

**Augmented Reality (AR) in Vocational Education: A Study on Two Principles of the Cognitive Theory of
Multimedia Learning (CTML) in AR and Their Effects on Students' Cognitive Load, Learning
Performance, and Motivation**

Master's Thesis

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Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training (SFUVET)

Author: Franz Lam (09-557-620)

Supervisors: Prof. Dr. Alberto Cattaneo
Head of the Research Field of Education Technologies in VET Programs
Research & Development, SFUVET

Dr. Sara Hutchison
Senior Lecturer and Senior Researcher, SFUVET

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Abstract

This study investigates the applicability of two key principles from the cognitive theory of multimedia learning (CTML)—the modality principle and the redundancy principle—in augmented reality (AR). While these principles have been extensively studied in traditional multimedia settings, their effectiveness in immersive technologies, such as AR, remains largely unexplored. Using a between-subjects design with three instructional conditions (audio-only, text-only, and audio and text combined), this study examined how different instructional modalities in AR influence cognitive load, learning performance, and motivation. A total of 104 apprentices from various vocational fields participated in the experiment, which involved learning a T-shirt folding technique using Microsoft HoloLens 2 AR goggles.

The results demonstrated that the expected advantages of audio over text (modality principle) and the disadvantages of redundant information (redundancy principle) were not observed in AR as they typically are in traditional multimedia environments, with no differences in intrinsic or extraneous cognitive load across the three conditions. However, the study found significant relationships between cognitive load and motivation; that is, higher perceived extraneous cognitive load was associated with lower perceived motivation levels, while higher perceived germane cognitive load correlated strongly with increased perceived motivation. Learning performance analysis suggested a trend favoring audio-based instruction (either alone or combined with text) over text-only instruction, although these differences did not reach statistical significance.

The findings indicate that the established CTML principles may operate differently in AR learning environments, highlighting the need for further investigation of these principles in AR. Additionally, the strong relationship identified between cognitive load and motivation highlights the importance of considering motivational factors when designing AR-based learning experiences. These results have important implications for the design of AR-based instructional materials, particularly in vocational education settings where procedural knowledge acquisition is crucial.

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Introduction

It has been proven that people learn content better when it consists of both visual (image, graphic, video, etc.) and verbal (oral or written text) information (Mayer & Fiorella, 2021a). The effective combination of different information in learning materials is theoretically based on the cognitive theory of multimedia learning (CTML), developed by Richard E. Mayer. CTML considers various principles so that the information to be conveyed can be optimally processed and retained by learners with the help of multimedia elements. The principles all follow the basic assumption that learners have limited cognitive resources available per time unit, referred to as “cognitive load,” whose components have to be properly balanced. Two of the basic CTML principles are the modality principle, which states that learners learn better from visuals and spoken words than from visuals and printed words, and the redundancy principle, which states that learners learn better if an explanation is not, in addition to image and audio, displayed as text (redundant information), as this leads to a higher cognitive load and learning performance is negatively affected.

While Mayer’s principles have a long list of empirical evidence in traditional multimedia, this is not yet the case for immersive environments, such as augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR). AR and VR are two terms that are everywhere in today’s technology-driven world. AR is a technology that combines virtual information with the real world (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017; Tekedere & Göker, 2016). In contrast to VR, where users see only a virtual environment, AR enables users to see the real world with an overlay of virtual elements, such as text, images, graphics, and other computer-generated elements. In short, the reality is augmented with virtual, digital information. However, despite their potential to fundamentally change (vocational) education, these technologies have not yet managed to establish themselves in education. Studies have shown that multimedia learning in an immersive environment brings various benefits, such as enjoyment and motivation, which in turn can have a positive impact on learning performance (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017; Cheng & Tsai, 2013; Makransky, 2021; Radu, 2014). Positive emotions experienced during learning, such as enjoyment, can enhance task focus and increase intrinsic motivation (Pekrun, 2006). This, in turn, can lead to a higher level of generative processing, also known as germane cognitive load (Makransky, Borre-Gude, et al., 2019). Moreover, immersive environments can potentially reduce extraneous cognitive load by shielding learners from external distractions and enabling them to focus better on virtual learning content (Baceviciute et al., 2021).

It is important to note that the research landscape is not uniformly positive. Several studies have shown more neutral or even contradictory findings regarding the effectiveness of these technologies for learning. Immersive environments can also lead to an increase in cognitive load because of the extended

visual field of view, which typically enhances their complexity (Makransky et al., 2021). Parong and Mayer (2018) found that students who learned about human anatomy using traditional methods (PowerPoint slides) outperformed those who used immersive virtual reality. They assumed that the novelty of VR might have distracted the students from the learning content. In Makransky, Terkildsen, et al.'s (2019) study, students using a desktop version of a science simulation learned more than those using a VR version. Students in the immersive VR condition had a higher cognitive load and learned less than students on a desktop computer. The authors assumed that the students in the immersive VR condition experienced a higher level of extraneous load and were too distracted from the learning content by the immersive environment. These findings underscore the complexity of implementing immersive technologies in educational settings and highlight the need for careful consideration of how these tools are integrated into the learning process.

Despite these challenges, research has suggested that AR may be particularly valuable in vocational education contexts, especially for teaching procedural knowledge. Zhang (2019) specifically investigated the use of AR for the acquisition of procedural knowledge, which is often challenging to convey in conventional learning settings. He revealed that students using AR significantly outperformed the control group in the long-term retention of procedural knowledge. This finding aligns with Makransky et al. (2021), who confirmed that immersion in multimedia learning environments can have a positive effect specifically when the learning objective is to enhance procedural knowledge. This type of knowledge is especially relevant for vocational education, as many vocational skills are based on practical processes and techniques.

Based on these premises, AR shows promising potential for vocational education. However, a key question remains regarding how to optimize the design of AR-based learning. While some studies have begun to investigate the application of CTML principles in VR, research specifically examining the modality and redundancy principles in AR remains limited. Makransky (2021) noted that while these principles are well established in traditional multimedia learning, their effectiveness in immersive technologies requires further investigation. In fact, in the latest edition of the *Cambridge Handbook of Multimedia Learning*, Mayer dedicated an entire chapter to immersive learning environments, acknowledging their unique characteristics and potential impacts on established multimedia learning principles. The current findings regarding these principles in immersive environments show mixed results. Albus and Seufert (2023) found that the modality effect actually reverses in VR. Some studies have demonstrated that the redundancy principle, which typically suggests avoiding the simultaneous presentation of identical content in different formats, might not apply in the same way in VR (Adesope & Nesbit, 2012; Ari et al., 2014; Moreno &

Mayer, 2002a; Moreno & Mayer, 2002b). These inconsistent findings highlight a significant gap in our understanding of how fundamental CTML principles translate to immersive technologies, and in particular to AR-based learning environments.

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the applicability of two key CTML principles—the modality principle and the redundancy principle—in AR. Specifically, we examine how different instructional modalities (audio-only, text-only, and combined audio and text) influence cognitive load, learning performance, and motivation when applied to AR-based instruction. By conducting a between-subjects experiment with 104 apprentices from various vocational fields, this research seeks to contribute to our understanding of effective instructional design in AR.

The findings of this study will have important implications for both theory and practice. From a theoretical perspective, they will help clarify how established multimedia learning principles apply in immersive learning contexts. From a practical standpoint, the results will provide valuable guidance for designing effective AR-based learning experiences, particularly in vocational education settings where procedural knowledge acquisition is crucial.

Theoretical Framework

This chapter lays out the theoretical foundations of multimedia learning that underpin the study conducted in this thesis by outlining the key theories and concepts. Central to this study is CTML by Richard E. Mayer, which provides a framework for designing effective multimedia instruction to promote meaningful learning.

Prior to delving into CTML, it is essential to provide a definition and establish a clear understanding of some key terms. When we hear *multimedia*, we might think of a term that is closely associated with the digital age, not realizing that multimedia has existed for centuries. Essentially, multimedia simply refers to the combined presentation of words, whether written or spoken, and pictures (Mayer & Fiorella, 2021a). In this sense, even pieces of paper with notes and sketches and books with written text and illustrations are examples of multimedia. With technological advancements, the methods of presenting pictures have broadened to include animated pictures, video, and even virtual elements in immersive environments. While multimedia encompasses the presentation of both words and pictures, *multimedia learning*, *multimedia instruction*, and *multimedia instructional messages* refer to the presentation of words and pictures to improve learning (Mayer & Moreno, 2003). The basic premise of multimedia learning is that combining words and pictures leads to deeper learning than using words alone. At this point, the question arises: Why do individuals learn better from words and pictures than from words alone? A comprehensive explanation is provided by Richard E. Mayer's CTML. It is a fundamental framework for multimedia learning based on the principle that the design of multimedia instructions should align with the ways in which humans process information to foster learning. When it comes to insights into human cognitive structures and how this knowledge can be used for effective instructional design, it is important to recognize that Mayer's CTML is grounded in several fundamental theories. These include cognitive load theory (Camp et al., 2021; Paas & Sweller, 2021; Sweller, 1988), Baddeley's (1986) model of working memory, the dual coding theory by Paivio (1991), and constructivist learning theories (Mayer et al., 1999). For the purposes of this study, cognitive load theory is particularly relevant, as it provides crucial insights into how cognitive processes impact learning by emphasizing the role of the working memory and the importance of managing cognitive load. Examining cognitive load theory will establish a solid foundation in the core concepts of human cognitive architecture and information processing and provide an important basic understanding before moving on to multimedia learning. Therefore, cognitive load theory will be examined in more detail before delving into CTML.

Cognitive Load Theory

Cognitive load theory was developed by John Sweller (1988). It was explicitly developed as a theory of instructional design that integrates aspects of human cognitive architecture and highlights the importance of understanding human cognitive processes in designing effective instruction (Sweller et al., 2011). Sweller pointed out that without knowledge of human cognitive processes, it is difficult to explain why instructional processes are successful or not, and this knowledge also involves understanding human cognitive structures and how these structures are organized into a cognitive architecture (Paas & Sweller, 2021).

Categories of Knowledge

To understand human cognition in instructional design, it is important to know the different categories of knowledge. According to Paas and Sweller (2021), cognitive load theory classifies knowledge into two categories based on Geary's (2007) framework: biologically primary and secondary knowledge. The ways knowledge is acquired, organized, and stored vary by category and each category requires different instructions (Paas & Sweller, 2021).

Biologically primary knowledge refers to knowledge that humans are evolutionarily predisposed to acquire, such as recognizing faces or speaking a first language. This type of knowledge is modular and developed at different stages of human evolution, making these skills largely independent of others. Due to this evolutionary development, humans can typically acquire biological primary knowledge faster, with minimal mental effort, and often even unconsciously. Consequently, primary knowledge does not require explicit instruction (Paas & Sweller, 2021).

Biologically secondary knowledge, on the other hand, refers to knowledge that is not acquired through evolutionary processes but is needed for cultural reasons. This type of knowledge is typically acquired consciously and with deliberate effort, often in educational settings such as schools (Paas & Sweller, 2021). Examples of biologically secondary knowledge include learning to read and solving mathematical problems. This knowledge is best acquired with explicit instructions (Paas & Sweller, 2021).

Human Cognitive Architecture

It is assumed that the acquisition of secondary knowledge is significantly influenced by human cognitive architecture encompassing both working memory and long-term memory. According to cognitive load theory, knowledge is stored in schemas within the long-term memory. For knowledge to be stored and organized in the long-term memory, the information must first be processed in the working memory (Paas & Sweller, 2021).

An explanation of how the human brain processes and stores information is provided by the multistore model of memory from 1968 by the two psychologists Atkinson and Shiffrin. Although this model has become outdated and has since been expanded with new components (e.g., Baddeley, 2000), it is still one of the most important and well-known memory models in psychology and is therefore still adequate for providing a basic understanding of how the human memory system works. As illustrated in Figure 1, the Atkinson–Shiffrin model assumes that human memory consists of three distinct storage types: sensory register, working memory, and long-term memory (Atkinson & Shiffrin, 1968), all of which are interconnected. CTML also relies on these three memory stores (Mayer, 2021).

Figure 1

Structure of the Memory System.

Note. Adapted from Atkinson and Shiffrin (1968).

Incoming information from the environment is captured by the sensory organs and then enters the sensory register (Schnotz, 2021). For example, a written text is perceived by the eyes and a spoken text by the ears. Information can then be stored and analyzed in a fraction of a second in the sensory register. This is like temporary storage that holds information just long enough to decide whether it is worth paying attention to. Only when the information is classified as relevant, and when attention is paid to it, will it be transferred to the working memory for further processing (Schnotz, 2021).

The working memory is a short-term storage system with both high complexity and limited capacity (Schnotz, 2021). It has two main functions: It can store limited information temporarily and, as its name suggests, process information (Schnotz, 2021). This processing of information is called encoding and takes place consciously (Mayer, 2021). Encoding is the initial step in memory formation, whereby sensory inputs (visual or auditory stimuli) are translated into mental representations to be stored in the

long-term memory and retrieved (Chan, 1997). It is important to note that, without active rehearsal, information in the working memory is typically stored for only a brief period, approximately 15–20 seconds (Goldstein, 2007). According to Baddeley (1986), the working memory can be divided into a visual channel to process visual information, an auditory channel to process auditory information, and a central executive, which acts as a supervisory system. It allocates resources between these two subsystems and it is also responsible for shifting our focus to relevant information (Baddeley, 2012). However, in the context of instruction, the primary interest lies in the two subsystems—the auditory and visual channels. In the working memory, visual and auditory information can be combined, organized, and linked with existing information from the long-term memory (Paas & Sweller, 2021).

Unlike the working memory, in the long-term memory, information is stored more permanently and in a more stable, interconnected network of schemas, or knowledge structures (Sweller, 2016). These schemas allow the efficient retrieval and application of stored information and play a crucial role in learning and problem-solving (van Merriënboer & Sweller, 2005). Cognitive load theory assumes that the long-term memory is unlimited in its capacity (Sweller et al., 2011). Information can be stored in the long-term memory as entirely new information, or it can be stored as a link to existing information in the long-term memory (Zoelch et al., 2019).

The main goal of instruction is to facilitate long-term learning (Soderstrom & Bjork, 2015). In this context, learning is generally considered to have occurred when information has been successfully encoded into the long-term memory and can be retrieved and applied when needed (Soderstrom & Bjork, 2015). More specifically, learning involves the construction of new schemas or the modification of existing ones based on newly acquired information (Sweller, 1994). These schemas are cognitive structures that organize and store knowledge, facilitating the efficient retrieval and application of information (Sweller, 1994). Paas and Sweller (2021) further described learning as a change in the long-term memory, stating that if no change has occurred in this memory, then no learning has taken place. This perspective aligns with the concept of durable learning proposed by Soderstrom and Bjork (2015), who argued that true learning involves the long-term retention and transfer of knowledge or skills.

Categories of Cognitive Load

Based on the human cognitive architecture described in the previous section, the acquisition of new knowledge involves close interaction between the working memory and the long-term memory (Sweller et al., 2011). However, before information can be transferred to the long-term memory, it must first be processed by the working memory, which has a limited capacity. Due to this limitation, the working memory cannot simultaneously process an infinite amount of information. To accommodate this constraint, cognitive load theory underlines the importance of carefully managing how new information is presented (Sweller, 1994; Sweller et al., 2011). Consequently, when new information is presented, it should be structured in a manner that reduces unnecessary processing to avoid cognitive overload and to enhance learning efficiency (Sweller et al., 2011). According to cognitive load theory, there are three different types of cognitive load: intrinsic (IL), extraneous (EL), and germane (GL).

Intrinsic Cognitive Load

IL refers both to the type of cognitive load that is inherent in the learning material and to the information to be learned itself (Sweller et al., 2011). Paas and Sweller (2021) described it as the “natural complexity of the biologically secondary information that must be processed” (p. 78). IL varies with the complexity of the information. As the information becomes more complex, IL increases (Sweller et al., 2011).

Extraneous Cognitive Load

In contrast to IL, which is determined by the complexity of the learning content, EL is imposed by the way it is presented (Sweller et al., 2011). This type of load is caused by the inappropriate presentation of learning materials. It is also related to the learning environment, the structure of the learning materials, and the conditions in which learning takes place. In other words, EL is imposed by the instructional design. Poor design leads to high EL, which means that learners must unnecessarily use their limited working memory resources to process instructional materials. Consequently, reducing EL as much as possible through improved instructional design is crucial for optimizing the learning process (Paas & Sweller, 2021; Sweller et al., 2011).

Germane Cognitive Load

GL is a process-related load that is necessary for understanding material and constructing new knowledge (Sweller et al., 2011). GL is the cognitive effort that a learner uses to engage actively with the learning content. Sweller et al. (2011) described it as working memory resources dedicated to information that is relevant to learning. One of the main targets of instructional design is to support generative processing, which refers to GL (Camp et al., 2021).

According to cognitive load theory, these three types of cognitive load are additive, meaning that they form a total load on the working memory during the learning process (Sweller et al., 2011). A cognitive overload occurs if this total load exceeds the capacity of the working memory, and learning becomes less effective. Learning instructions have to be designed in a way that minimizes EL and ensures enough cognitive resources for GL. This is especially important when high IL is expected due to the complexity of the learning content (Sweller et al., 2011). According to Paas and Sweller (2021), GL does not necessarily have to be high if the IL for a learning task is low. If the learning content is relatively simple and easily comprehensible, the instructional design may have less impact on the learning process.

In summary, it can be said that the primary goal of cognitive load theory is to present learning content in a way that reduces unnecessary processing in the working memory while enhancing aspects that facilitate processing and storing biologically secondary knowledge in the long-term memory.

Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning

Building upon the foundations of cognitive load theory, Richard E. Mayer developed the CTML to specifically address how people learn better from combining words and pictures. The focus of CTML then lies on how to design learning material using words and pictures in ways that foster meaningful learning. While cognitive load theory provides a general framework for understanding cognitive processes in learning, CTML focuses on the challenges and opportunities presented by multimedia instruction. CTML is based on the following three core assumptions, which align with but extend beyond those of cognitive load theory.

Dual Channel

As discussed in the previous chapter, it is assumed that humans process information through two separate channels of working memory: one for visual information and another for auditory information (Mayer, 2021a). This assumption aligns closely with Baddeley's (1986, 2012) model of working memory, which includes two key components: the visuospatial sketchpad and the phonological loop. The visuospatial sketchpad handles both the processing and short-term storage of visual and spatial information, corresponding to the visual channel in CTML. The phonological loop, on the other hand, handles auditory and verbal information, aligning with the auditory channel in CTML.

Visual information, such as pictures, videos, and written texts, is captured by the eyes and processed in the visual channel, while auditory information, such as narrations and music received through the ears, is processed in the auditory channel (Mayer, 2021a). Following this assumption, learning material presented as images and written text exploits only the visual channel but not the auditory channel. This situation could lead to an overload of the visual channel and result in diminished learning

performance without exploiting the potential of the auditory channel at all. However, if, in the given example, a narration is provided along with an image, the cognitive load can be distributed through both channels. As a result, the cognitive load on a single channel can be reduced, and information processing becomes more effective. It is assumed that the verbal and visual channels are equivalent, meaning that words and pictures are two equivalent ways of presenting the same material (Mayer & Fiorella, 2021a).

Limited Capacity

The reason for the previously described channel overload is that the working memory and each of its channels has a limited capacity to process information simultaneously (Mayer, 2021). This means that the working memory can handle only a limited number of pieces of information simultaneously. For example, when people look at an illustration, they can store only a limited number of information in the visual channel of their working memory. Miller's (1956) article on storage capacity limits revealed that the capacity for information processing in the working memory is about 7 ± 2 units (chunks) of information. In his research, participants were able to remember and recall between five and nine units of information, such as numbers or images. More recent studies have suggested that there is an even lower capacity limit. For instance, Cowan (2001) proposed that working memory capacity is limited to only 3–5 chunks of information. An important note is that the size of these chunks can vary depending on the expertise of the individual (Cowan, 2001; Gobet & Simon, 1998).

Active Processing

CTML assumes that learning is an active process (Mayer, 2021). Learners do not just passively receive information when they learn from multimedia. Instead, they actively engage with the presented material. Meaningful learning occurs when learners actively process information, which involves three key cognitive processes: selecting, organizing, and integrating. First, learners need to select relevant material by shifting attention to the relevant words and pictures in the material being presented. This initial step entails the transfer of external stimuli into the working memory. In the next step, the selected material needs to be organized in the working memory. This involves creating connections and relationships among the selected elements. For example, selected words are mentally organized to create a coherent and meaningful verbal representation. The last part of active processing involves the integration of incoming selected material with existing knowledge. Prior knowledge from the long-term memory is activated and called back to the working memory, where the interaction of prior and new knowledge takes place. In this phase, connections between the verbal and pictorial models are built up, creating new schemas or adapting preexisting ones. This process of active engagement with the learning material closely relates to the concept of GL in cognitive load theory (Sweller et al., 2011). The active

processing involved in selecting, organizing, and integrating information, as described in CTML, can be seen as the learner's investment in cognitive resources, which contributes to GL.

These core assumptions form the foundation for understanding how humans process multimedia information. In the process of building connections between words and pictures, Mayer's CTML assumes that "learners are able to create a deeper understanding than from words or pictures alone" (Mayer & Fiorella, 2021a, p. 8). This concept is at the heart of CTML and has been supported by various studies (Carney & Levin, 2002; Levie & Lentz, 1982; Mayer & Fiorella, 2021a).

To optimize learning based on these assumptions, Mayer developed several principles that guide the design of effective multimedia materials. These principles aim to reduce extraneous processing (referring to EL), optimize essential cognitive processing (referring to IL), and foster generative processing (referring to GL) in multimedia learning (Mayer, 2021). In the first edition of his work, he introduced 22 principles of multimedia design (Mayer, 2005). By the second edition of his handbook, Mayer had expanded the number of principles to 25 (Mayer, 2014b). In the most recent edition of *The Cambridge Handbook of Multimedia Learning*, Mayer discussed 31 principles (Mayer & Fiorella, 2021c). This gradual increase in the number of principles reflects the ongoing research and refinement of CTML over two decades, demonstrating how the understanding of multimedia learning has deepened and become more refined over time.

This study focuses on two key principles that are particularly relevant to our research context: the principles of modality and redundancy.

The Modality Principle in Multimedia Learning

Building on the exploration of CTML, which established the enhanced effectiveness of learning through the combined use of words and pictures, this chapter transitions to an examination of the first principle to be investigated in this study: the modality principle. The term "modality" refers to the sensory modalities of humans (Scheiter et al., 2020), describing the different types of perceptions available to them. In the context of education, the particular interest is to differentiate between information processing through visual perception via the eyes and auditory perception via the ears (Scheiter et al., 2020). It is important to note that Mayer categorized the modality principle as a strategy for managing essential processing in multimedia learning. This means that this principle is primarily aimed at optimizing the handling of IL. The modality principle suggests pairing instructional images with spoken narration rather than written text (Castro-Alonso & Sweller, 2021). In other words, using a spoken text together with an image is better than using a written text combined with an image. However, this applies only to short and simple narrations (Castro-Alonso & Sweller, 2021). One possible explanation of the modality

principle is the split-attention effect, which states that when learners view an image and read the corresponding text, they must divide their visual attention between both sources of information, which are physically disparate (Ayres & Sweller, 2021; Kalyuga et al., 1999). This forces the learners to shift their attention frequently between the image and the written text, resulting in an increase in EL. However, with narrated text, attention can be fully focused on the image. In addition to the split-attention effect, the modality principle can also be explained by CTML (Castro-Alonso & Sweller, 2021). As mentioned in the chapter on CTML, this theory assumes that the working memory consists of two separate channels: one for processing visual information and one for processing verbal information. If an image and written text are used for a learning unit, both types of information must be processed by the visual channel, which can lead to an overload of the working memory. If spoken text is used instead, information processing can be divided between both channels (Moreno & Mayer, 1999). According to Castro-Alonso and Sweller (2021), the simultaneous use of both channels increases the total capacity of the working memory. Sweller (2011) emphasized that the split-attention effect, and thus the modality principle, comes into effect only when both sources of information are incomprehensible on their own. Both sources of information must complement each other to understand the learning content. No modality effect is generated if the text describes only the image.

Studies have also shown that the effect of the modality principle varies depending on the initial situation. A meta-analysis by Ginns (2005) not only supported the modality principle but also revealed that its effect is stronger with more complex learning material and with system-paced instead of learner-paced instruction. Seufert et al. (2009) found a stronger modality principle for learners with low prior knowledge than for learners with high prior knowledge. This aligns with the findings of Kalyuga et al. (2000), who demonstrated that for inexperienced learners, the most advantageous format paired visual diagrams with simultaneous audio narration, further supporting the modality principle. Additionally, Moreno and Mayer (1999) found that learners showed better comprehension when animations were paired with spoken explanations rather than with written text, providing further evidence of the benefits of audiovisual presentations in multimedia learning.

While the modality principle suggests that spoken words are generally more effective than written text when paired with visual information, recent research in VR has shown results that challenge this assumption in immersive learning environments. Baceviciute et al. (2020) conducted a study on VR that provided evidence contrary to the traditional modality effect. Their findings indicated that participants in the text condition remembered more information than those in the audio condition. Participants reported lower difficulty scores for both EL and IL when information was presented as text rather than audio.

However, the study also revealed some advantages of the audio condition in VR. Participants in this condition demonstrated higher extraneous attention scores, suggesting better recall of visual information in the VR environment. Additionally, EEG analyses indicated that audio presentation resulted in a lower mental memory load and effort than textual presentation. These findings suggest that in VR, text might be better for the retention of presented information, while audio may be less mentally demanding for learners.

Research on the modality principle in immersive technologies, such as VR and AR, is still limited. The few existing studies have produced mixed results, sometimes supporting (Ginns, 2005; Seufert et al. 2009) and sometimes contradicting (Baceviciute et al., 2020) the modality principle. This lack of consistent findings highlights the need for more research to understand how this principle applies in immersive learning environments.

The Redundancy Principle in Multimedia Learning

As anticipated, the foundations of CTML say that learning content can be better understood when it includes both words and images rather than just words. Independent of the modality principle we just discussed, words can be presented both verbally and in written form. Some might think that combining images with both verbal and written words would be beneficial and could lead to better learning. However, more is not always better, especially when it comes to providing additional information to learners. Studies have shown that redundant information can hinder learning rather than enhance it (Kalyuga et al., 1999; Kalyuga & Sweller, 2021). Redundant information refers to additional information that is not necessary for learning and could be presented simultaneously in different forms, such as orally and in writing, as well as completely irrelevant information (Kalyuga & Sweller, 2021). According to cognitive load theory, the redundancy principle can be explained considering that processing redundant information leads to an increase in EL. Limited cognitive resources are then spent processing unnecessary information that does not contribute to the learning goal or processing the same information twice in both channels. Therefore, according to this principle, all redundant information should be avoided in multimedia instruction. As indicated by Fiorella and Mayer (2021b), the redundancy principle is primarily aimed at reducing extraneous processing (EL) in multimedia learning.

Kalyuga et al. (1999) demonstrated a redundancy effect by finding that learners who were only presented with auditory explanations performed better than those who received both visual and auditory texts. They concluded that duplicating auditory information visually significantly impairs learning by increasing cognitive load. However, other research has challenged this principle, showing that redundant information can be beneficial under certain conditions. A meta-analysis by Adesope and Nesbit (2012)

revealed that the benefits of redundancy were particularly evident for participants with low prior knowledge and in system-paced instructional settings. In studies with learner-paced learning material, they did not find benefits for redundant presentations. Their meta-analysis also demonstrated that learners with weak reading or language skills benefitted from redundant information. Additionally, they found that redundancy was beneficial when learning materials were picture-free. Supporting this finding, Moreno and Mayer (2002b) observed that learners better comprehended explanations when text was combined with narration, but only when no other visual material was presented simultaneously. This suggests that redundancy can be beneficial in the absence of competing visual information and may allow learners to process redundant textual information more effectively. Interestingly, Ari et al.'s (2014) results seem to contradict some of these findings. They observed that the redundancy effect reversed under specific conditions: complex learning material, short redundant text, and self-paced learning. This suggests that redundant information can be beneficial even in self-paced environments, contrary to the findings of Adesope and Nesbit's (2012) meta-analysis.

These contrasting results highlight the complexity of the redundancy effect and suggest that its impact may depend on a combination of factors. In summary, research findings have shown that redundant information can be beneficial for learners with low prior knowledge and weak reading or language skills when dealing with complex material or when no competing visual information is present. The impact of learner-paced instruction on the redundancy effect remains unclear.

The redundancy principle has also been investigated in immersive learning environments. Moreno and Mayer (2002a) investigated the effect of redundancy in a VR simulation. They found no difference between the audio and redundancy conditions, but both conditions significantly outperformed the text-only condition. Similarly, Baceviciute et al. (2021) carried out a study in which the participants learned through an immersive VR application. Their study compared three different instructional modalities: audio-only, text-only, and a combination of audio and text (redundancy condition). The results showed that the participants in the redundancy condition had comparable performance to those in the text-only condition. However, both groups significantly outperformed the participants in the audio-only condition. Makransky, Terkildsen, et al. (2019) investigated the redundancy effect in their study by comparing desktop and immersive versions of a VR science simulation. They found no redundancy effect in either condition.

These studies provide insights into the redundancy effect of VR. However, research specifically examining this effect in AR is much more limited, indicating a need for further investigation in this area.

Other Principles of CTML Applied in this Study

While this study focuses primarily on the modality and redundancy principles, several other principles from CTML were incorporated into the development of the AR application. These additional principles were implemented to ensure that the overall design of the learning experience was aligned with the CTML framework. Table 1 provides an overview of these applied principles, with brief descriptions. The specific ways in which these principles were integrated into the AR application are detailed in the Methods section.

Table 1

Principles of CTML Applied in this Study.

Principles	Description	References
<u>Principles with the aim of reducing intrinsic cognitive load</u>		
Segmenting	People learn better when multimedia messages are split into chunks rather than as a whole unit.	Mayer and Chandler (2001), Mayer and Fiorella (2021b)
<u>Principles with the aim of reducing extraneous cognitive load</u>		
Coherence	People learn better when irrelevant information is excluded.	Fiorella and Mayer (2021b), Harp and Mayer (1997)
Signaling	People learn better when cues are added to identify the relevant information or to show how the material is structured.	Mautone and Mayer (2001), Van Gog (2014)
Spatial contiguity	People learn better when corresponding words and pictures are presented close to each other.	Fiorella and Mayer (2021b), Mayer (1989)
Temporal contiguity	People learn better when related words and pictures appear simultaneously rather than one after another.	Fiorella and Mayer (2021b), Mayer and Anderson (1991)
<u>Other principles applied in this study</u>		
Voice	People learn better when narration comes from a natural human voice instead of a computer-generated voice.	Fiorella and Mayer (2021a), Mayer et al. (2003)
Animation	People learn better from dynamic graphics, such as animations, than static graphics.	Wong et al. (2009), Höffler and Leutner (2007)

Multimedia Learning in AR

As anticipated, while the redundancy and modality principles are well established in traditional multimedia learning environments, their applicability to immersive technologies, such as VR and AR, remains largely unexplored. The unique characteristics of these immersive environments, including an increased sense of presence and interactivity, may influence the cognitive processes underlying these principles in ways not accounted for by traditional multimedia tools.

AR has emerged as a promising technology in educational contexts that offers unique opportunities for multimedia learning. In their comprehensive review, Akçayır and Akçayır (2017)

highlighted several advantages of AR in education. They noted that AR can enhance learning outcomes, motivation, and student engagement. The technology allows for the visualization of complex spatial relationships and abstract concepts, making it particularly useful in fields such as science and engineering. Radu (2014) corroborated these findings in his meta-review, emphasizing that AR can lead to better learning performance, increased content understanding, and improved long-term memory retention than traditional media. He also noted that AR can enhance collaboration among students and between students and instructors. Moreover, Akçayır and Akçayır (2017) suggested that AR can provide immediate and contextual information, potentially reducing cognitive load by presenting information in a more intuitive manner. This aligns with findings from Ibáñez and Delgado-Kloos (2018), who specifically examined AR in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics learning. They reported that AR can support situated learning by providing context-aware information that enhances the understanding of complex phenomena. However, the implementation of AR in education is not without challenges. Akçayır and Akçayır (2017) pointed out issues such as technical problems, the difficulty of maintaining student attention on learning goals rather than the novelty of the technology, and the need for additional time and effort in preparing AR-enhanced learning materials. Radu (2014) added to this list, mentioning potential usability difficulties and the risk of cognitive overload if AR interfaces are poorly designed. Despite these challenges, researchers generally agree on AR's potential. Ibáñez and Delgado-Kloos (2018) concluded that AR can significantly improve learning, particularly in areas requiring spatial abilities, practical skills, or conceptual understanding. They also noted AR's capacity to increase student motivation and foster positive attitudes toward learning. Given the demonstrated potential of AR to enhance learner motivation, it is crucial to examine the broader role of motivation in learning processes.

Motivation

Motivation in the context of learning is defined as the degree of effort a learner is willing to put into achieving a learning goal (Keller, 2010). Extensive research has established that motivation plays a critical role in enhancing learning performance (Brunstein & Heckhausen, 2010; Deci & Ryan, 1985; Hattie, 2008; Schiefele & Schaffner, 2020). While the impact of motivation on learning is well documented, this study focuses specifically on how instructional design can influence motivation, particularly in AR-based learning environments. Understanding how to design motivating instructions is crucial, especially when implementing new technologies, such as AR, in educational settings. As observed by Akçayır and Akçayır (2017), Ibáñez and Delgado-Kloos (2018), and Radu (2014), the use of AR for learning can boost student motivation. Thus, these studies underscore the importance of considering motivational factors in AR-based learning environments. Astleitner et al. (2006) emphasized motivation as a learning-relevant

parameter and criticized existing multimedia learning theories, including Mayer's CTML, for inadequately addressing motivational factors. Mayer himself acknowledged the limitations of CTML regarding motivation. In describing the cognitive processes central to his theory, he explicitly stated, "Also not shown are motivation, which powers the learner's effort to engage in the processes" (Mayer, 2021, p. 65). Furthermore, Mayer (2014a) emphasized that an important underspecified aspect of cognitive theories of multimedia learning is the role of motivation. This admission highlights a significant gap in CTML's framework, as it does not account for the motivational forces that drive learners' engagement with multimedia content. Mayer (2014a) suggested that incorporating motivational elements can enhance student learning by promoting generative processing—in other words, germane cognitive load. While the impact of motivation on learning has been extensively studied in general educational contexts, its specific application in multimedia learning is a relatively recent development (Schrader et al., 2021). CTML was expanded into the cognitive-affective theory of learning with media proposed by Moreno (2006), acknowledging the role of motivation and affect in multimedia learning (Moreno & Mayer, 2007; Schrader et al., 2021). However, despite this theoretical recognition, motivation has remained largely unexplored in most CTML studies. Most research still focuses primarily on the cognitive aspects of multimedia learning.

Keller's (1987) ARCS model of motivational design provides a theoretical framework for examining motivation in the context of instructional design. This model is rooted in expectancy-value theory, which assumes that motivation is influenced by the individual's confidence in their capability to accomplish a task (expectancy aspect) and the perceived importance or usefulness of the task (value aspect) (Keller, 1987). Through research and a synthesis of motivational theories, Keller (1987) extended this to four key conditions that must be met for individuals to become and remain motivated during instruction. The ARCS model of motivational design proposes that instructional designers can systematically improve learner motivation by focusing on the following four conditions (Keller, 1987, 2010):

Attention: This condition involves capturing and maintaining the learner's interest. Keller suggested using strategies such as perceptual arousal (e.g., surprising or intriguing elements) and inquiry arousal (e.g., posing questions or problems) to stimulate curiosity and sustain engagement.

Relevance: This refers to making the learning experience meaningful to the learner. It involves connecting the content to the learner's personal goals, past experiences, or future applications. Keller emphasizes the importance of answering the question "Why should I learn this?".

Confidence: This condition focuses on helping learners develop positive expectations for success. It includes providing clear objectives, opportunities for success at varying levels of challenge, and personal control over learning. The goal is to build learners' belief in their ability to succeed.

Satisfaction: This final condition relates to reinforcing accomplishments. It involves providing intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, recognizing achievement, and giving learners opportunities to apply what they have learned. The aim is to make learners feel good about their learning experiences and achievements.

Building upon Keller's (1987) ARCS model, instruments were developed to measure motivation in instructional settings. One of these instruments is the Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS), which was designed to assess learners' motivational reactions to instructional materials (Keller, 2010). More recently, a condensed version called the Reduced Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (RIMMS) was introduced (Loorbach et al., 2015). The RIMMS offers a significant advantage as a short, validated scale for measuring motivation that remains consistent with the ARCS model.

The Interaction of Cognitive Load and Motivation

While cognitive load and motivation have often been studied separately in educational research, the complex relationship of how these two factors interact with each other in the context of the learning process has increasingly been recognized (Evans et al., 2024; Feldon et al., 2019; Mayer, 2014a; Paas et al., 2005). The way in which learning material is presented and processed (cognitive load) can significantly impact the willingness of learners to engage with the material (motivation), and vice versa, learners' motivation can influence how they allocate cognitive resources. This interaction becomes particularly relevant when considering the different types of cognitive load and their possible impact on learner motivation.

Feldon et al. (2019) suggested that a high cognitive load might negatively affect motivation. They proposed that cognitive load could create psychological stress, which might decrease learner motivation. This reduced motivation could then worsen the effects of EL as learners become less willing to put mental effort into the task. In an experimental study with science students, Feldon et al. (2018) found that high EL negatively affected students' belief in their self-efficacy over time, regardless of their performance. On the other hand, when EL was reduced, student motivation increased (Evans et al., 2024; Martin, 2016; Wang et al., 2022).

In contrast to EL, GL has been found to have a positive relationship with motivation. Paas et al. (2005) argued that GL is closely associated with motivational processes, stating that it "can be considered as reflecting the actual amount of invested mental effort in learning, which is related to motivation" (p.

28). This suggests that higher levels of GL may be related to an increased motivation to engage with the learning material. Moreno and Mayer (2007) emphasized that even when cognitive resources are available, learners may not engage in generative processing (GL) without adequate motivation, further supporting this positive relationship. In a later work, Mayer (2014a) explicitly addressed this connection, discussing how instructional design that promotes GL can enhance motivation, further reinforcing the positive relationship between these two learning components. In their study, Schnotz, and Kürschner (2007) showed how GL is related to deeper processing and learning, which can increase motivation through a sense of accomplishment and understanding of the task.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

Building on the theoretical foundations discussed in the previous sections, this study aims to investigate the applicability of two key principles from CTML—the modality principle and the redundancy principle—in an AR learning environment. While these principles have been extensively studied and validated in traditional multimedia settings, their effectiveness in immersive technologies, especially in AR, remains largely unexplored. Specifically, we seek to understand how these principles influence students' cognitive load, motivation, and learning performance when applied to AR-based instruction.

To address these aims, the following research questions and hypotheses have been formulated:

1. General Question: How do the modality and redundancy principles apply in AR environments?
 - RQ1.1: How does the modality principle apply in AR?
 - H1: IL is lower in the audio-only conditions than in text-only or audio and text conditions.
Justification: Previous research in VR environments (Baceviciute et al., 2020) has shown that audio presentation results in a lower mental memory load and effort compared to textual presentation. As AR shares immersive characteristics similar to VR, we expect comparable effects in our AR setting. Additionally, CTML suggests that presenting visual information combined with text or with text and audio can overload the visual processing channel, as both require a visual processing capacity (Mayer, 2021). Since the modality principle specifically aims to manage IL by optimizing the use of both visual and auditory channels (Castro-Alonso & Sweller, 2021), we hypothesize that IL is lower in the audio-only condition than in the text-only or audio and text conditions.
 - RQ1.2: How does the redundancy principle apply in AR?
 - H2: There are no significant differences in EL between the audio-only, text-only, and combined audio and text conditions.

Justification: According to CTML, the redundancy principle aims to reduce EL, which means redundant information typically leads to increased EL (Kalyuga & Sweller, 2021). Based on this principle, simultaneously presenting information through audio and text should result in higher EL than through single-modality presentations. However, recent studies in VR environments have challenged this traditional understanding (Makransky, Terkildsen, et al., 2019; Moreno & Mayer, 2002a). Therefore, based on the similarities between AR and VR, we hypothesize that there are no significant differences in EL between the audio-only, text-only, and combined audio and text conditions.

2. General Question: How do different instructional modalities in AR affect learning performance?

- RQ2.1: How do different instructional conditions (audio-only, text-only, and audio and text combined) influence learning performance, as measured by the number of attempts required to successfully complete the learning task?
 - H3: Learners in the audio-only and text and audio conditions require fewer attempts to successfully complete the learning task than those in the text-only condition.

Justification: This prediction is based on the study by Moreno and Mayer (2002a), which showed that both audio-only and combined audio-text presentations outperformed text-only conditions in VR learning environments.

3. General Question: What is the role of motivation when learning in AR?

- RQ3.1: How do EL and GL influence learner motivation in AR?
 - H4: Learners experiencing higher levels of EL report lower levels of motivation.
 - H5: Learners experiencing higher levels of GL report higher levels of motivation.

Justification: Studies have shown that high EL can create psychological stress that negatively impacts motivation (Feldon et al., 2019), and when EL is reduced, student motivation increases (Evans et al., 2024). Conversely, GL has been found to have a positive relationship with motivation, as it reflects the actual cognitive resources devoted to learning (Paas et al., 2005). Studies have demonstrated that increased GL correlates with higher motivation (Moreno & Mayer, 2007). Based on these findings, we hypothesize that learners experiencing higher levels of EL report lower levels of motivation, while learners experiencing higher levels of GL report higher levels of motivation.

Methods

This chapter outlines the methodological approach used in this study. To address the research questions, an experimental study was conducted using a between-subjects design with three different instructional conditions in AR: audio-only, text-only, and audio and text combined. This design was chosen to allow for a direct comparison of the effects of different instruction modalities on cognitive load, learning performance, and motivation. The following sections provide detailed information on the sample, ethical considerations, measures and instruments used, materials, procedure, and data analysis methods employed in this study.

It is important to note that the data collection for this study was conducted in collaboration with researchers from the Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training (SFUVET) and the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI). This collaboration was part of a broader national research project funded by the State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation. While the present study focuses on cognitive load, learning performance, and motivation in AR environments, the associated study incorporated additional measures, including the NASA Task Load Index (Hart & Staveland, 1988). These additional measures are mentioned in the procedure section for completeness, but the data from these measures are not analyzed or reported in the current study. This collaborative approach allowed for the efficient use of participant time and resources while enabling multiple research questions to be addressed.

Sample

Two vocational schools in the canton of Bern were contacted to recruit participants. Both schools took part. An a priori power analysis run with G*Power calculated with an alpha error of .05, an effect size of $f = .40$, and a power of .80 indicated a required total sample size of 66 participants. Finally, 104 apprentices participated in this study. There were 11 female (10.6%) and 93 male (89.4%) participants, who ranged in age from 15 to 37 years ($M = 17.26$, $SD = 2.70$). The participants were apprentices for vocational training at the level of a Federal Diploma of Vocational Education and Training and enrolled in the Logisticians, Gardeners, Information Technologists, and Automotive Technicians curricula. The schools selected which students would take part and which school classes would participate. This study was conducted with intact and entire school classes—although the apprentices participated individually in the experiment—and each participating class was comprised of students who were all training for the same profession.

Ethical issues

Prior to participating, all apprentices received an informed consent form (see Appendix A for the complete consent form). The form outlined the study's objectives and assured participants that the collected data would be used exclusively for scientific purposes. It emphasized the protection of their privacy, stating that personal data would be anonymized and not traceable back to the individual. The participants were informed that their participation was voluntary; they could withdraw their consent at any time, in which case their data would no longer be used for the research; and any non-anonymized material would be destroyed. Additionally, it was stated that personal data would be destroyed 10 years after the project's completion. By signing the consent form, the participants authorized the researchers to use the collected information for scientific purposes, including dissemination in scientific publications and presentations at academic conferences.

Measures and Instruments

In this study, we measured three key variables—cognitive load, learning performance, and motivation—using a combination of validated scales and task-specific measurements.

The cognitive load scale developed by Krieglstein et al. (2023) was used to measure the participants' cognitive load in this study. All items from the cognitive load scale were already available in German. This scale was chosen for several reasons. First, it is a new instrument grounded on a recent theoretical understanding of cognitive load, giving it relevance in current research. Second, the scale was designed to measure different types of cognitive load and is therefore in line with the multifaceted nature of cognitive load theory. Finally, it has been validated in educational settings, which makes it appropriate specifically for this study. The cognitive load scale consists of three subscales: one for intrinsic cognitive load (IL), one for extraneous cognitive load (EL), and one for germane cognitive load (GL). Each subscale contains five items. The participants were asked to respond to each item using a seven-point Likert scale ranging from *strongly disagree* (1) to *strongly agree* (7). The complete Krieglstein Cognitive Load Scale, including all items translated into German, is provided in Appendix B.

Learning performance was assessed through multiple measures, including the number of attempts, duration of task completion, and accuracy of the folded T-shirts. For each folding task, the participants were first evaluated for their ability to successfully complete the fold within the given time limit. Task completion was coded as a binary outcome, with 1 indicating successful completion and 0 indicating failure to complete the task. For those who successfully completed the task, accuracy was then measured. The folded T-shirt was measured at six different points (as illustrated in Figure 2), and the results were compared to the measurements of an ideally folded T-shirt.

Figure 2

Measuring Points of Folded T-shirts.

Note. A = right shoulder, B = left shoulder, C = total shoulder, D = belly, E = side length 1, F = side length 2

Accuracy was quantified as the sum of the differences (delta) between a participant's measurements and the ideal measurements at these six points. This approach allowed for a comprehensive assessment of both the participant's ability to execute the learned technique and the precision with which they could apply it. As the learning task was self-paced, we decided to define learning performance only as the number of attempts required to successfully complete the folding technique in the learning task. The number of attempts served as a proxy for the ease with which the participant acquired the new skill, with fewer attempts indicating faster learning. This measure was chosen because it reflects a participant's ability to understand and replicate the folding technique without time pressure, allowing for a more natural learning process.

To evaluate the motivation of the participants, the RIMMS developed by Loorbach et al. (2015) was employed. For this study, all items of the RIMMS scale were translated from English to German. The choice of the RIMMS was based on its efficiency as a short form of the widely used IMMS while still having robust psychometric properties and theoretical grounding. This was especially important due to the time constraints of the data collection. The RIMMS specifically targets motivation in self-directed instructional

settings, which is well suited for the context of this research, considering that it is an AR-based learning environment. Additionally, this survey is based on Keller's (1987) ARCS model of motivational design, which provides a tough theoretical framework for understanding motivation in learning contexts. Moreover, the RIMMS has been validated for use with technology-based instruction and is thus highly relevant to the current study, which focuses on learning in AR. The RIMMS consists of four subscales, each of which stands for one of the constructs of the ARCS model: attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction. Each of these subscales is comprised of three items. The participants were asked to respond to each item using a seven-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7). The complete RIMMS scale, with all items translated in German, is provided in Appendix C.

All scales were checked for reliability using McDonald's omega (ω), which was always above the minimum threshold of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019; Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). The only adaptation made to the scales involved the IL subscale. Due to the slightly lower—although acceptable—reliability of the IL subscale ($\omega = 0.728$), one item (IL 2) was removed to obtain a significantly higher reliability score ($\omega = 0.817$). All details of the reliability tests are reported in Table 2.

Table 2

Reliability Tests for the Scales Used to Test Cognitive Load and Motivation.

Scale	Subscale	No. of items	ω	95% CI
Cognitive load (Krieglstein, 2023)	IL	4	0.817	[0.761, 0.873]
	EL	5	0.805	[0.745, 0.864]
	GL	5	0.816	[0.759, 0.872]
RIMMS (Loorbach et al., 2015)	Attention	3	0.948	[0.933, 0.963]
	Relevance	3		
	Confidence	3		
	Satisfaction	3		

Note. IL = intrinsic cognitive load, EL = extraneous cognitive load, GL = germane cognitive load, RIMMS = Reduced Instructional Materials Motivation Survey.

Materials

For data collection and the execution of the experimental tasks, the following materials and tools were utilized:

AR Device – Microsoft HoloLens 2: For the folding exercises conducted in this study, the second generation of HoloLens by Microsoft was used (see Figure 3). HoloLens 2 is a head-mounted display that provides a highly immersive experience. The device allows for precise tracking of hand movements and spatial mapping, making it ideal for complex AR applications. For this study, each researcher had access to two HoloLens 2 devices. This ensured that, while one device was being used, the other could be charged, allowing for continuous operation. This setup was crucial for maintaining the pace of data collection and minimizing the potential EL on the participants. By eliminating the waiting times between sessions that could occur if a single device had to be recharged, the risk of participants becoming distracted or disengaged was reduced. Additionally, having a second device readily available provided a quick fallback option in case of any unexpected application errors. The HoloLens 2 devices were provided by SFUVET.

Figure 3

Microsoft HoloLens 2.

AR Application for T-Shirt Folding: The AR application used in this study was originally developed by SFUVET for a previous study comparing video instructions with AR instructions. For the current research, this application was adapted with minor modifications to suit the specific requirements for investigating CTML principles in an AR context. The AR application began with an instructional video demonstrating the complete T-shirt folding technique from start to finish. This video, which was identical for all participants regardless of their experimental condition, provided a comprehensive overview of the folding procedure. After watching the video, participants proceeded to the interactive learning phase

where they received guided instructions according to their assigned condition. The application contained three distinct task sequences, one for each experimental condition (audio-only, text-only, and text and audio). Each sequence guided participants through the learning, retention, and transfer tasks specific to their assigned condition. The application was developed in alignment with the CTML principles discussed in the theory chapter, with the primary goal of verifying the applicability of the modality and redundancy principles in AR. Several CTML principles were incorporated into the design. First, to reduce IL, the task was divided into several phases (segmenting principle), allowing participants to process information in manageable chunks (see Figure 4).

Figure 4

Instructional Video Demonstrating the Folding Technique.

Second, to reduce EL, only essential information was provided in the verbal instructions for completing each step, thereby avoiding distracting details (coherence principle). Third, visual and verbal elements were presented closely in space and time (spatial and temporal contiguity principles). Fourth, white spheres were used to highlight key information (signaling principle), particularly to indicate hand placement for correct T-shirt folding (see Figure 5). This was especially useful for steps involving complex or unfamiliar gestures.

Figure 5

White Spherical Markers to Highlight the Correct Hand Positions.

Fifth, for steps in which the folding gesture was difficult to imagine or unfamiliar, animations were used (animation principle). This is particularly helpful for learners when procedures involve movements that are complex to understand (see Figure 6).

Figure 6

Animations in Green to Illustrate the Required Movements.

Sixth, in conditions in which information was provided orally, a human voice was used to deliver the audio information (voice principle).

T-Shirts for the Folding Exercises: For this study, a variety of T-shirts were employed for the different folding tasks to assess the participants' ability to learn, retain, and transfer the folding technique. The following types of shirts were used:

- **Medium-sized T-shirt:** This was the primary T-shirt used in the study. It was utilized for the initial learning task, in which the participants first learned the folding technique. The same medium-sized T-shirt was used again in the retention task, in which the participants attempted to replicate the folding technique without guidance. This T-shirt was also used for the first of the three transfer tasks, in which it was rotated by 180 degrees to test the participants' ability to apply the technique to a familiar shirt in a new orientation.
- **Smaller T-shirt:** For the second transfer task, a T-shirt of smaller dimensions was positioned in the same orientation as the learning task, with the neckline to the right. This shirt was used to assess the participants' ability to adapt the learned folding technique to a different-sized garment.

- Polo shirt: A polo shirt was used for the third and final transfer task. This shirt type was chosen to test the participants' ability to apply the folding technique to a different style of shirt with features such as a collar and buttons. Additionally, the polo shirt was rotated by 90 degrees (neckline at the top) for this task, further challenging the participants' ability to transfer the learned technique to a new context.

Measurement tools: A flexible measuring tape was used to take the measurements at each point. Measurements were taken in centimeters and millimeters. A digital stopwatch was used to precisely time each folding task. For the learning task, timing began when the participant first touched the T-shirt and ended when they completed the fold. In the retention and transfer tasks, the stopwatch was used to ensure adherence to the time limits (60 seconds for retention and 90 seconds for each transfer task). A laptop computer was used on-site for immediate data entry. An Excel spreadsheet was prepared in advance with columns for all the data to be collected.

Procedure

The data collection for this study was conducted by a team of researchers, including the author of this thesis. To ensure consistency and reliability in the data collection process, all the researchers completed preliminary training based on a standardized protocol. This protocol was developed to cover all aspects of the experimental procedure, including participant interaction, device setup, task administration, and data recording. Depending on the availability of the researchers, the data collection was conducted in 1–3 parallel sessions over a period of 2 weeks. Each participant was allowed to be absent from regular school lessons for a maximum of 45 minutes to take part in the study. Prior to individual participation, a general presentation of the study was conducted in front of the entire class. During this presentation, the researchers introduced the study's objectives and informed the students that they would be learning how to fold a T-shirt using an AR device. The presentation also covered the specific data that would be collected and its intended use, mirroring the information provided in the consent form. This approach allowed for a more efficient process, as participants were already familiar with the study's details before their individual sessions. Following the presentation, the class teacher sent one participant after the other to one of the rooms prepared for this study. The participants were initially greeted, and gratitude was expressed for their voluntary participation in the study. Given that they had already been briefed during the class presentation, the participants were asked if they had any questions or concerns before proceeding. They were then provided with the consent forms and asked to review them briefly to ensure that they understood and agreed to the terms. This process saved time while ensuring that each participant gave informed consent. Once they had signed up, the study began. To ensure randomization

and equitable distribution across the three conditions, the participants were alternately assigned to each condition.

At the beginning of each session, the participants were asked to demonstrate any T-shirt folding techniques with which they were familiar. This allowed the researcher to record the variety of folding methods known to the participants and to ensure that none of them already knew the specific folding technique to be learned in this study. None of the 104 participants knew of this technique. Subsequently, the researcher prepared the HoloLens 2 to ensure its correct setup for the participants' use. This preparation involved starting the device and running the eye calibration before handing it over to the participants. The participants were then guided through the eye calibration process through instructions provided directly by the device. Eye calibration is a crucial step in ensuring that the holographic content appears in the correct spatial positions relative to the participant's environment and field of view. It also facilitates precise hand tracking and enables the participant to interact seamlessly with the holographic elements. After calibration, the researcher had to put on the HoloLens 2 once again to launch the first folding task. Before handing over the device, the researcher had to position the T-shirt frame on the table, which the participants would see during the task. This step was essential for the proper functioning of the AR application. The T-shirt frame served as a spatial anchor and reference point for the AR system, allowing it to accurately overlay virtual instructions onto the physical environment. By ensuring that the frame was correctly positioned, the researcher guaranteed that the AR elements would appear in the right location relative to the actual T-shirt, thus maintaining the spatial consistency necessary for the participants to follow the folding instructions accurately. This precise alignment between the virtual guidance and the physical task space was crucial for the validity of the experiment and the participants' learning experience.

Part 1: Learning Task

Before the learning task began, the researcher advised the participants to pay close attention to the visual instructions and, depending on the condition, to listen to and/or read them carefully. In the learning task, the participant first watched an instructional video on how to fold the T-shirt. This video was the same for all participants in the study and was displayed directly within the HoloLens 2. After the video ended, the participants were asked by the application to fold a T-shirt on their own using the technique shown. The researcher handed them a T-shirt. On the table in front of them, the participants saw the outline of this T-shirt projected by the HoloLens 2. The application instructed them to spread out the T-shirt on the table so that it fit within the displayed outlines. The participants received guidance on hand placement, hand movement, and finger grip on the fabric via AR animations superimposed onto the

T-shirt. In addition to the visual instruction, the participants in the audio-only condition also received oral instructions played through the built-in speakers of the device. The participants in the text-only condition received the same instructions but as written text, which was displayed in their field of vision. The participants in the audio and text condition received both oral and written instructions. Figure 7 shows the different presentations of the instructions.

Figure 7

Differences in the Presentation of the Instructions.

The researcher recorded how long it took for the participants to complete the folding, starting from the moment they grabbed the T-shirt until the folding was finished. The researcher was not allowed to assist the participants with the folding technique. Only hints related to device handling were allowed, and such hints were noted in the data table. If a participant encountered difficulties in successfully folding the T-shirt following the provided instructions, they were given the opportunity to repeat the exercise. There was no limit to the number of attempts—participants could retry the folding process as many times as they needed or desired to achieve successful folding. The number of attempts was also recorded in the data table. Participants who successfully completed the folding were assigned code 1 in the data table, while those who did not manage were assigned code 0; these participants were not permitted to proceed to the second task (retention task). After this learning task, the participants set the device aside. They were then asked by the researcher to scan with their mobile phones a QR code that directed them to a survey delivered using Qualtrics software. The participants were required to answer the questionnaire, including measures for cognitive load and motivation. While the participants answered the questions, the researcher took measurements of the folded T-shirts.

Part 2: Retention Task

The participants were again asked to stand in front of the table and put on the device. Again, they saw the outlines of the T-shirt projected onto the table. The researcher handed the T-shirt to each participant and instructed them to lay it out on the table so that it would fit within the outlines. They were

informed that they now had 1 minute to attempt the most accurate fold possible using the technique learned earlier. During this minute, the participants were allowed to restart multiple times, if needed. The researcher began timing each participant from when they started folding the shirt until they were satisfied with their result, within 1 minute. After folding, the participants were asked to set aside the device and proceed with the questionnaire. They were informed that the questions were the same as some questions they had previously answered (NASA Task Load Index), but this time, these questions were related to the task just completed. While the participants answered the questions, the researcher took the same measurements on the T-shirts as in the learning task. The participants who managed to complete the folding were assigned code 1 in the data table, while those who were unable to complete the task were assigned code 0; they were then ineligible to proceed to the next task (transfer task).

Part 3: Transfer Task

In the final part of the study, the participants were asked to perform three more folds: once with the same T-shirt rotated by 180°, once with a much smaller T-shirt oriented in the same way as in the learning task, and once with a polo shirt rotated by 90° (see Figure 8).

Figure 8

Shirts Used in the Three Transfer Tasks.

For each task, they were given 90 seconds to achieve the best fold possible. At the end, they had to answer the questions of the Nasa Task Load Index related to the transfer tasks one more time. The study was then completed for the participants.

The entire experimental procedure for each participant lasted approximately 35–40 minutes, of which approximately 15 minutes were dedicated to answering the questionnaires. Table 3 provides an overview of the procedure, including the specific time limitations for the folding tasks.

Table 3

Overview of the Full Procedure.

Step	Description	Time limit
<u>Learning Task</u>		
1	Watch the instructional video on how to fold the T-shirt using a specific technique	
2	Fold the T-shirt under the guidance of the application	
3	Answer the questionnaire (RIMMS, Cognitive Load, Nasa Task Load Index)	
<u>Retention Task</u>		
4	Fold the T-shirt with the learned technique by themselves	60 sec.
5	Answer the questionnaire (Nasa Task Load Index)	
<u>Transfer Task</u>		
6	Fold the T-shirt rotated by 180°	90 sec.
7	Fold a much smaller T-shirt	90 sec.
8	Fold a Polo-shirt rotated by 90°	90 sec.
9	Answer the questionnaire (Nasa Task Load Index)	

Data Analysis

After data collection, two spreadsheets were prepared for data analysis. The first spreadsheet contained the data from the folding tasks, including the participants' names, ages, and assigned conditions. It further detailed numerical data for each folding task, noting task completion (1 for passed, 0 for not passed), folding time, and the measurements from the folded T-shirt. Crucial for data analysis was the delta between the participant's fold and the ideal fold, which is a perfectly symmetrically folded T-shirt. Consequently, additional columns were included in which this delta was calculated.

The second spreadsheet captured responses from the Qualtrics survey. This survey was structured into three sections: questions referring to the learning task in the first section, the retention task in the second section, and the transfer task in the third section. Following this, the two spreadsheets were merged into one. All names of the participants were then removed from all the sources, with each participant provided with an anonymized identifier. To ensure the reliability of the dataset, potential biases were checked. This involved examining the responses for any patterns and looking for indications of confirmation bias. After that, an outlier analysis was conducted on the number of attempts at the learning task ($M = 1.54$, $SD = 0.751$). Two participants out of 103 (1 value was missing) required four attempts, which were identified as potential outliers. These cases were retained in the analysis, as they represented a very small proportion (1.94%) of the sample. The data were analyzed using Jamovi open statistical software (Version 2.4.14).

The initial plan for data analysis involved the use of analysis of variance to examine the differences among the three experimental conditions. However, preliminary analysis revealed that the data violated the assumption of normality. Given this violation of the normality assumption, the statistical approach was adjusted to use nonparametric methods that did not assume a normal distribution of the data. Specifically, the Kruskal–Wallis test was selected as the primary method of analysis. To test the association between the variables, simple linear regression was used.

Results

This chapter presents the findings of the study. The results are organized and presented in accordance with the order of the research questions and hypotheses. Initially, descriptive statistics for cognitive load components and motivation across the three instructional conditions (audio-only, text-only, and audio and text combined) are provided. Subsequently, the results of hypothesis testing are presented, addressing each of the five hypotheses.

Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive statistics for cognitive load components across the three instructional conditions (Table 4) revealed several patterns. IL appeared highest in the text-only condition ($M = 2.82$, $SD = 1.52$) and lowest in the audio-only condition ($M = 2.27$, $SD = 1.34$). EL was equal and highest in both the text-only ($M = 2.54$, $SD = 1.44$) and text and audio conditions ($M = 2.54$, $SD = 1.10$) but lower in the audio-only condition ($M = 2.22$, $SD = 1.26$). Overall, the audio-only condition appeared most favorable, with the lowest IL and EL and the highest GL.

Table 4

Descriptive Statistics of Cognitive Load by Conditions.

	Condition	N	Mean	SD	SE
IL	A	35	2.27	1.34	0.226
	T	34	2.82	1.52	0.261
	TA	35	2.41	1.19	0.201
EL	A	35	2.22	1.26	0.213
	T	34	2.54	1.44	0.248
	TA	35	2.54	1.10	0.185
GL	A	35	6.44	1.70	0.288
	T	34	6.42	1.79	0.306
	TA	35	6.24	1.52	0.257

Note. IL = mean of all IL items except for one item (IL2), EL = mean of all EL items, GL = mean of all GL items.

The descriptive statistics (Table 5) for motivation, measured using the RIMMS scale, showed that the audio-only condition consistently had the highest or near-highest mean scores across all four motivation sub-scales, while the text and audio condition showed the lowest scores in all subscales except for satisfaction.

Table 5*Descriptive Analysis of the RIMMS Scale.*

	Condition	N	Mean	SD	SE
Attention	A	35	5.53	1.23	0.208
	T	34	5.28	1.43	0.245
	TA	35	5.05	1.37	0.232
Relevance	A	35	5.39	1.44	0.243
	T	34	5.40	1.16	0.199
	TA	35	4.99	1.27	0.215
Confidence	A	35	5.85	1.26	0.213
	T	34	5.41	1.27	0.218
	TA	35	5.40	1.25	0.212
Satisfaction	A	35	5.62	1.38	0.234
	T	34	5.41	1.59	0.272
	TA	35	5.57	1.31	0.221

Note. A = audio-only condition, T = text-only condition, TA = text and audio condition.

Results of Hypothesis Testing

This section presents the statistical analyses conducted to test the five hypotheses of this study.

Hypothesis 1

To test the hypothesis that IL is lower in the audio-only condition than in the text-only and audio and text conditions, a Kruskal–Wallis test was conducted. The analysis revealed no significant difference in IL among the three instructional conditions ($\chi^2 = 2.81$, $p = .246$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.0273$). These results do not support the hypothesis that IL differs significantly across instructional conditions.

Hypothesis 2

The second hypothesis posits that there are no significant differences in EL between the audio-only, text-only, and audio and text conditions in the AR. To examine this, another Kruskal–Wallis test was employed. The results ($\chi^2 = 2.29$, $p = .319$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.0222$) showed that there was no significant difference in EL among the three conditions. Hypothesis 2 is supported by our data.

Hypothesis 3

To examine the differences in the number of attempts required across the three instructional conditions, a Kruskal–Wallis test was conducted. The test revealed a statistically significant difference in the number of attempts among the three conditions ($\chi^2 = 7.07$, $p = .029$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.0693$).

Pairwise comparisons were performed using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons (Table 6).

Table 6

Pairwise Comparisons of the Number of Attempts Across Instructional Conditions.

		W	p
T	TA	-3.179	0.063
T	A	-3.204	0.061
TA	A	-0.305	0.975

Note. T = text-only, TA = text and audio, A = audio-only. Significance level: $p < .05$.

While the overall Kruskal–Wallis test indicated significant differences among the conditions, the pairwise comparisons did not reach the threshold for statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). However, the comparisons between text-only and the other two conditions (text and audio as well as audio-only) were at the cusp of significance ($p = .063$ and $p = .061$, respectively). These results provide partial support for Hypothesis 3 and suggest a trend toward participants in the text-only condition requiring more attempts compared to those in the audio-only and text and audio conditions, although these differences were not statistically significant.

Hypothesis 4

To examine the hypothesis that learners experiencing higher levels of EL report lower levels of motivation, a linear regression analysis was conducted. EL was used as the predictor variable, with overall motivation as the outcome variable. Both the intercept ($\beta = 6.354$, $SE = 0.2299$, $t = 27.64$, $p < .001$) and the effect of EL ($\beta = -0.389$, $SE = 0.0840$, $t = -4.63$, $p < .001$) were significant, with an overall R^2 of 0.174 (adjusted $R^2 = 0.166$). This suggests that the higher the EL, the lower the motivation level. The moderate correlation between EL and motivation ($R^2 = 0.174$) indicated that 17.4% of the variance in motivation could be explained by EL. The overall model demonstrated statistical significance ($F(1, 102) = 21.5$, $p < .001$), suggesting that in this context, EL is a meaningful predictor of motivation. Figure 9 visually illustrates the negative relationship between EL and motivation. The downward slope of the regression line clearly depicts how motivation tended to decrease as EL increased.

Figure 9

Regression of Perceived EL on Perceived Motivation.

Note. Motivation = mean of all four RIMMS subscales, EL = mean of all three EL subscales.

These results provide strong support for Hypothesis 4, which posits that learners experiencing higher levels of EL report lower levels of motivation.

Hypothesis 5

A linear regression analysis was conducted to test the hypothesis that learners who experience higher levels of GL report higher levels of motivation. GL was used as the predictor variable, with overall motivation as the outcome variable. The results indicated a strong positive correlation between GL and motivation ($R = 0.704$). Both the intercept ($\beta = 2.210$, $SE = 0.3302$, $t = 6.69$, $p < .001$) and the effect of GL ($\beta = 0.502$, $SE = 0.0502$, $t = 10.01$, $p < .001$) were significant, with an overall R^2 of 0.495 (adjusted $R^2 = 0.491$). GL accounted for nearly half of the variance in motivation, showing that GL can strongly predict motivation. Figure 10 depicts the positive relationship between GL and motivation. The upward trajectory of the regression line clearly demonstrates that as GL increased, motivation levels tended to rise correspondingly.

Figure 10

Regression of Perceived GL on Perceived Motivation.

Note. Motivation = mean of all four RIMMS subscales, GL = mean of all three GL items.

These results also provide strong support for Hypothesis 5, which proposes that learners experiencing higher levels of GL report higher levels of motivation.

Discussion

This study investigated the applicability of two key principles of CTML—the modality principle and the redundancy principle—in AR. Furthermore, the research explored how different instructional conditions influenced cognitive load, learning performance, and motivation when applied to AR-based instruction. In the following sections, we discuss each of our hypotheses in light of the reported results.

Applicability of the Modality and Redundancy Principles in AR

The first research question focused on the applicability of the modality and redundancy principles in AR. Based on these principles, we hypothesized that IL would be lower in the audio-only condition than in the text-only and audio and text conditions (Hypothesis 1). We also predicted that there would be no significant differences in EL between the three conditions (Hypothesis 2). Contrary to expectations based on CTML, the study found no significant differences in either IL or EL among the three instructional conditions. CTML posits that the modality principle optimizes IL and that the redundancy principle aims to reduce EL. If these principles were directly applicable to AR environments, we would expect to observe significant differences in cognitive load across the three conditions. However, the absence of such differences suggests that these principles may not be directly transferable to AR-based learning contexts.

Although the inferential statistics showed no significant differences between conditions, the descriptive analyses revealed an interesting trend: the audio-only condition exhibited the lowest EL, the lowest IL, and the highest GL. This pattern, while not statistically significant, aligns with some aspects of CTML. The lower IL in the audio-only condition suggests that the learners in this group perceived the task as less inherently complex or difficult. For instance, they might have found it easier to follow the folding instructions when they were presented audibly without the need to shift attention between the visual text and the physical task. The lower EL in the audio-only condition indicates that these learners might have experienced less cognitive strain from the instructional design itself. They may have found it more straightforward to process the auditory instructions while simultaneously performing the folding task without the potential distraction of reading on-screen text. Conversely, the higher GL in the audio-only condition shows that these learners might have been more actively engaged in processing and integrating new information. They could have devoted more cognitive resources to understanding and applying the folding technique rather than managing the presentation format of the instructions.

The fact that there was no strong modality effect in our study can be related to the findings of previous research on the conditions under which the modality principle has the greatest impact. Ginns's (2005) meta-analysis showed that the modality effect is typically stronger with more complex learning materials and in system-paced rather than learner-paced instructional settings. In our study, the T-shirt

folding task, although novel to all the participants, may not have reached the level of complexity whereby the benefits of the modality principle became evident. Moreover, our learning task was learner paced, allowing the participants to learn the folding task at their own speed. This self-pacing might have reduced the potential cognitive overload that the modality principle aims to address. Additionally, Seufert et al. (2009) found that the modality principle had a stronger effect on learners with low prior knowledge. While our participants likely had low prior knowledge of the specific folding technique, the task itself—folding a T-shirt—was a familiar procedure. This familiarity might have reduced the overall cognitive demand, potentially diminishing the advantages that audio presentation might offer in more cognitively demanding scenarios. These three factors combined may explain why a strong modality effect was not observed in this study. Our findings indicate that while the modality principle remains a viable approach in AR, its applicability is constrained by several factors. These include task complexity, pacing, and learners' prior knowledge, which may influence the extent to which the modality principle can be applied in this context.

Having discussed our findings for the modality principle, we now turn our attention to the redundancy principle and its applicability in AR. Similar to our findings regarding the modality principle, our results showed no significant differences in EL between the three instructional conditions. This outcome challenges the traditional understanding of the redundancy principle, which posits that learners learn better when the same information is not simultaneously presented in multiple formats (Kalyuga & Sweller, 2021). However, these results align with recent studies in immersive learning environments. For instance, Makransky, Terkildsen, et al. (2019) found no redundancy effect in their comparison of desktop and immersive versions of a VR science simulation. Similarly, Moreno and Mayer (2002a) observed no difference between audio and redundancy conditions in a VR simulation, while both outperformed the text-only condition. Moreover, our findings align with an expanding body of research indicating that the impact of redundancy may be more intricate than previously assumed, even in traditional learning environments. Adesope and Nesbit's (2012) meta-analysis found that the effects of the redundancy principle were not the same in all learning conditions. They found that redundant presentations can be more beneficial for learners with low prior knowledge than purely spoken presentations, especially in systems-based learning environments. Our participants likely had low prior knowledge of the specific T-shirt folding technique that was taught, which aligns with the conditions in which Adesope and Nesbit (2012) found potential benefits of redundancy. However, our task was learner paced, a condition for which Adesope and Nesbit (2012) suggested redundant information might be less helpful. These counteracting factors could explain why we observed neither a clear advantage nor a clear disadvantage of redundancy in our AR learning environment. This highlights the complex interplay between learner

characteristics, task design, and the effectiveness of redundant information in immersive learning contexts.

Impact of Instructional Modalities in AR on Learning Performance

The results revealed a significant difference in the number of attempts among the three conditions. While pairwise comparisons did not reach conventional levels of statistical significance, they suggested a trend toward participants in the text-only condition requiring more attempts than those in the audio-only or audio and text conditions. These findings partially support our hypothesis that learners in the audio-only and audio and text conditions require fewer attempts to successfully complete the learning task than those in the text-only condition. The trend toward better performance in the audio-only and audio and text conditions is consistent with the modality principle of CTML, which suggests that people learn better from graphics and narration than from graphics and on-screen text (Mayer & Moreno, 2003). In our context, the audio instructions may have allowed the participants to focus their visual attention on the folding task without the need to divide their attention between reading the text and performing the folding. These findings align closely with those of Moreno and Mayer (2002a), who found no difference between audio and redundancy conditions in a VR simulation. However, both conditions outperformed the text-only condition. The performance trend in favor of audio-based instruction (either alone or combined with text) could also be related to the nature of the task. Learning to fold a T-shirt is a procedural, hands-on task that might benefit more from auditory instructions, allowing learners to maintain a visual focus on the physical task. This aligns with the findings of Zhang (2019), who found that AR was particularly effective for the acquisition of procedural knowledge. It is important to note that our study was conducted using a relatively simple short-term learning task. The effects we observed might differ for more complex or long-term learning scenarios in AR.

Role of Motivation when Learning in AR

The second research question explored the role of motivation when learning in AR. Specifically, we examined how EL and GL relate to motivation. Our findings support the hypothesis that learners experiencing higher levels of EL report lower levels of motivation. This negative relationship aligns with cognitive load theory and extends its implications to AR environments. As Sweller et al. (2011) posited, EL is imposed by poor instructional design and does not contribute to learning. Our results suggest that in AR contexts, instructional elements that increase EL not only hinder learning but also diminish learner motivation. This finding is particularly relevant in consideration of one of the assumptions made by Feldon et al. (2019) that high cognitive load can negatively influence motivation by creating psychological stress. In the context of AR learning, in which users navigate through both real and virtual elements, poorly

designed instructions could lead to increased EL, potentially causing stress and reducing motivation. This highlights the importance of careful instructional design in AR to minimize EL, not only to facilitate learning but also to maintain learner motivation.

While EL had a negative impact on motivation, our findings regarding GL revealed a contrasting and strong positive relationship. This relationship aligns with and extends previous research. The strong positive correlation we observed between GL and motivation suggests that as learners engage more deeply with the learning material (higher GL), their motivation to learn also increases. This finding is consistent with the theoretical framework proposed by Paas et al. (2005), who argued that GL reflects the actual mental effort invested in learning, which is closely tied to motivation. The results also align with the findings of Moreno and Mayer (2007). While their study focused on classical but interactive learning environments, our results extend their findings to AR environments, suggesting that the positive relationship between GL and motivation holds true in more immersive, interactive learning contexts. The findings on the impact of GL on motivation have important implications for the design of AR learning experiences. They suggest that AR instructional designs should aim to optimize GL by providing learning activities that promote deep engagement with the material. This might involve interactive elements that prompt learners to actively process and apply the information they are learning, rather than passively receiving it.

However, it is important to note that while our study shows a relationship between EL and GL with motivation, causality cannot be definitively established from our correlational design. The negative correlation between EL and motivation and the positive correlation between GL and motivation provide valuable insights but do not prove that changes in cognitive load directly cause changes in motivation or vice versa. Future research could employ experimental designs to further explore the causal relationships between different types of cognitive load and motivation in AR.

In addition, it should be taken into account that the novelty of the AR device and the AR application itself may have contributed to the high levels of motivation observed in this study. The fascination we observed among the participants for this new technology may have led to a “novelty effect,” temporarily boosting their enthusiasm and engagement (see Limitations section for a detailed discussion of this effect). While this effect does not negate our findings, it does suggest that the relationship between GL and motivation in AR environments may evolve as learners become more accustomed to such tools.

Limitations

Despite our best efforts to conduct a comprehensive study, several limitations should be acknowledged.

Lack of a Usability Assessment

A significant limitation of this study was the absence of any assessment of the usability of the AR device and the application used. We did not incorporate measures to evaluate how easily participants could use and interact with the AR device and application, which is a crucial factor when implementing new technologies in learning environments. In their systematic review, Akçayır and Akçayır (2017) identified usability issues as among the most frequently reported challenges concerning AR applications. They pointed out that technical problems and difficulties in using AR technology can be significant barriers to its effective implementation in educational settings. Similarly, Cheng and Tsai (2013) emphasized that the perceived ease of use of AR systems is a key factor influencing the attitudes and behavioral intentions of learners toward using these technologies for educational purposes. By not assessing these factors, our study may have overlooked the important influences on our results. For example, participants who found the AR interface to be more intuitive and easy to use might have experienced lower EL, regardless of the instructional modality. It is important to note that the decision not to include a usability assessment was made primarily due to resource constraints, particularly time limitations. Participants already required up to 40 minutes to complete the exercise and answer the questions. We did not consider it reasonable or feasible to extend this time further to accommodate additional usability-related questions. While this decision allowed us to maintain a manageable study duration for the participants, it did come at the cost of not capturing potentially valuable usability data.

Sample Limitations: Gender Imbalance and Limited Professional Diversity

Our study has interrelated limitations concerning the composition of our sample—namely, a significant gender imbalance and a restricted range of represented professions. These factors collectively impact the generalizability of our findings, highlighting important considerations for future research in AR-based learning environments. Due to the nature of the participating vocational classes, there was a significant gender imbalance in our sample (89.4% of the participants were male). Given that previous research has shown that gender can affect experiences with and attitudes toward technology (Cai et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2013), the imbalance may have influenced our results. Therefore, further investigation with more balanced gender representation is recommended. In addition, our study was conducted with participants from a limited number of vocational professions, based on which schools and training

programs agreed to participate. This limitation may affect the generalizability of our findings to other professional contexts or educational settings.

Novelty Effect

A further limitation of this study is the potential influence of the novelty effect associated with the use of a new technology (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017). The novelty effect describes how performance tends to temporarily increase when users first encounter new technology. This effect is not due to any actual improvement in learning or achievement but is due to the increased motivation to use the new technology (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017; Chwo et al., 2018). Hsiao et al. (2012) highlighted this issue in their study on AR-based learning. They pointed out that when AR is increasingly used in educational settings, the learning attitudes and motivation of students might not remain as positive as they are when the technology is first introduced. Similarly, Di Serio et al. (2013) noted that the motivational impact of AR in educational settings could be partially attributed to its novelty. They observed increased levels of attention and satisfaction among students using AR for the first time but cautioned that these effects might diminish as students become more familiar with the technology. In addition, Akçayır and Akçayır (2017) noted that the novelty of AR technology could lead to temporary increases in student motivation and engagement, which might not persist over time. This underscores the need for longitudinal studies to distinguish between the effects of AR as an instructional tool and the temporary boost provided by its novelty. In the context of our study, the participants' engagement and performance might have been influenced by the excitement of using AR technology rather than solely by the instructional design itself.

Limitations in the Learning Measurement

Due to resource constraints, we were able to conduct only a single measurement at one point in time, focusing solely on the learning task. This approach, while practical, fell short of capturing the full spectrum of learning outcomes. Theoretical frameworks (e.g., Soderstrom & Bjork, 2015) emphasize the importance of transfer tasks in providing crucial indicators of whether true learning has taken place. Moreover, our measurement of learning performance was limited to the number of attempts without considering the time taken (speed) or the precision of the folding (measured as the deviation from a perfect fold). These additional metrics could have provided a more comprehensive view of the learning outcomes. The decision to focus on a single metric was again due to resource limitations, which restricted our ability to conduct more extensive analyses. This simplified approach to measuring learning performance may not have fully captured the nuances of skill acquisition and application in the context of AR-based instruction.

Translation of Validated Scales

One methodological limitation was the translation of the validated scales from English to German. While care was taken to ensure accurate translation, there is always a possibility that subtle nuances in meaning could have been altered, potentially affecting the validity of the measures in the German context.

Relevance for Theory and Practice

This study contributes to both the theoretical understanding of CTML principles in AR environments and the practical implementation of AR in vocational education.

From a theoretical perspective, this study reveals that well-established CTML principles, such as modality and redundancy, may function differently in AR environments than in traditional multimedia settings. The absence of significant differences in cognitive load between instructional modalities suggests that AR may create unique cognitive processing patterns that are not fully captured by traditional multimedia learning theories. Additionally, our findings on the relationship between cognitive load and motivation in AR learning environments—specifically, that germane load positively correlates with motivation, while extraneous load negatively affects it—extend our theoretical understanding of how cognitive and motivational factors interact in immersive learning contexts.

For vocational education practice, our findings offer valuable insights for implementing AR-based instruction. While not statistically significant, our results indicate that audio-based instruction (either alone or combined with text) tends to perform better than text-only instruction. This finding is particularly relevant for vocational training tasks in which learners need to maintain a visual focus on physical objects or procedures. Furthermore, the demonstrated relationship between cognitive load and motivation provides important considerations for designing AR-based vocational training materials. These insights can help guide the development of more effective AR-based learning applications and experiences in vocational education settings.

Further Research

Based on the findings of this study, several key areas could benefit from further investigation. One possible direction for future research is the examination of the interaction between usability and learning outcomes in AR environments. Although our study revealed significant correlations between cognitive load and motivation, we did not investigate the potential moderating role of usability in these relationships. Additionally, a more nuanced investigation is needed regarding the relationship between different types of motivation and cognitive load in AR. While our study demonstrated clear correlations between cognitive load and overall motivation, future research should differentiate between intrinsic and extrinsic motivations to better understand these relationships. For instance, studies could examine

whether intrinsic motivation might help learners better manage cognitive load or whether extrinsic motivation affects different aspects of cognitive load differently. Furthermore, longitudinal studies are needed to investigate how to sustain learner motivation beyond the initial novelty effect of AR technology. Such research would be valuable for developing AR learning experiences that maintain engagement and effectiveness over extended periods of use.

Conclusions

The aim of this study was to advance our understanding of two multimedia learning principles in AR by examining how different instructional modalities affect learning, cognitive load, and motivation. Through a between-subjects experiment with 104 apprentices, this study provided several important insights. Our findings suggest that the traditional understanding of the modality and redundancy principles may not directly transfer to AR-based learning environments. Although we found no statistically significant differences in cognitive load between instructional conditions, the observed trends suggest that there are potential advantages of audio-based instruction in AR. Perhaps most significantly, our study revealed important relationships between cognitive load and motivation in AR-based learning. The negative correlation between EL and motivation, coupled with the strong positive relationship between GL and motivation, underscores the importance of considering both cognitive and motivational factors when designing AR learning experiences. These results have important implications for the design of AR-based educational content. While traditional multimedia learning principles remain relevant, they should be applied thoughtfully and adapted to account for the unique characteristics of AR environments. As educational technology continues to evolve, these findings contribute to a growing understanding of how to effectively leverage AR for learning.

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Declaration of Originality

I hereby confirm that I have written this thesis independently, have not used any sources other than those stated, and have collected and processed the data in accordance with scientific standards. I have marked all passages that were taken verbatim or in context from sources as such. I acknowledge that I used AI language models, specifically ChatGPT-4, Claude 3.5 Sonnet, and DeepL Write, to assist with phrasing optimization and language refinement in this thesis. My work is not a case of plagiarism. I am aware that any infringement will result in a grade of F, SFIVET is entitled to withdraw the title awarded based on this thesis, and any legal action will be reserved (Art. 4 and 23 of the SFIVET Study Regulations).

Date: 20th of November 2024

Signature:

Appendix A

Form of Consent

EINWILLIGUNGSERKLÄRUNG

- Die Forschung, für die wir um Ihre informierte Einwilligung bitten, ist sowohl Teil einer Masterarbeit als auch einer Dissertation an der EHB. Die Dissertation ist zudem auch in einem nationalen Projekt eingebunden, das in Zusammenarbeit mit der Fachhochschule Südschweiz (SUPSI) durchgeführt wird und vom Staatssekretariat für Bildung, Forschung und Innovation (SBFI) finanziert wird.
- Als Teil des Masterstudiums an der EHB soll eine Abschlussarbeit verfasst werden, bei der es um die Untersuchung der Kognitiven Theorie des Multimedialen Lernens (KTML) in Augmented Reality geht. Es soll herausgefunden werden, wie sich unterschiedliche Instruktionen in AR auf das Lernen auswirken.
- Die gesammelten Daten werden auch in einer Dissertation von einem Forschenden an der EHB verwendet, mit dem Ziel, die Rolle der KTML bei der Reduzierung der kognitiven Belastung bei der Verwendung von AR zu erforschen.
- Die Forschungsergebnisse werden Aufschluss über die Wirksamkeit dieser Technologien bei der Unterstützung des Erlernens von Abläufen geben und als Grundlage für die Entwicklung von Anwendungen dienen, die komplexere Abläufe unterstützen können.

Forschende: Alberto Cattaneo, Vito Candido, Chiara Locatelli, Franz Lam

Kontaktperson: Franz Lam franz.lam@studierende.ehb.swiss - T. +41 79 518 36 83
Alberto Cattaneo mail: alberto.cattaneo@ehb.swiss - T. +41 58 458 25 24

Ich bestätige hiermit, dass ich umfassend informiert worden bin:

- über die betreffende Forschung und ihre Ziele;
- dass die gewonnenen Daten ausschliesslich für wissenschaftliche Zwecke verwendet werden, wobei die Privatsphäre der Teilnehmenden in vollem Umfang geschützt bleibt;
- dass die persönlichen Daten der Unterzeichnerin/des Unterzeichners in passwortgeschützten Computern gespeichert werden und nicht für andere Zwecke verarbeitet oder an Dritte weitergegeben werden;
- dass persönliche Daten anonymisiert werden, so dass sie nicht mehr zur Unterzeichnerin / zum Unterzeichner zurückverfolgt werden können;
- dass personenbezogene Daten zehn Jahre nach Beendigung des Projekts vernichtet werden;
- dass die Teilnahme völlig freiwillig ist und dass ich das Recht habe, diese Einwilligung jederzeit zu widerrufen. In diesem Fall werden die Daten ab dem Zeitpunkt des Widerrufs nicht mehr für die Forschung verwendet und alles noch nicht anonymisierte Material wird vernichtet;

und ich ermächtige hiermit die Forschenden der Projekte:

• die gesammelten Informationen zu den oben genannten Zwecken zu verbreiten,	Ja <input type="checkbox"/>	Nein <input type="checkbox"/>
○ in wissenschaftlichen und fachlichen Publikationen zu verwenden,	Ja <input type="checkbox"/>	Nein <input type="checkbox"/>
○ und an wissenschaftlichen Kongressen zu präsentieren.	Ja <input type="checkbox"/>	Nein <input type="checkbox"/>

Der/die Unterzeichnete
(in Großbuchstaben)

.....

Ort und Datum

Unterschrift

.....

.....

Appendix B

Cognitive Load Scale (Kriegelstein et al., 2023)

ICL

ICL1 Die Lerninhalte waren schwer zu verstehen

ICL2 Die Erklärungen des Lerninhalts waren schwer nachvollziehbar

ICL3 Die Lerninhalte waren komplex

ICL4 Die Lerninhalte enthielten viele komplexe Informationen

ICL5 Ohne Vorwissen waren die Informationen nicht verständlich

ECL

ECL1 Es war schwierig, einen Überblick über den Aufbau des Lernmaterials zu erlangen

ECL2 Die Gestaltung des Lernmaterials machte es schwer, die Zusammenhänge zwischen den einzelnen Informationen herzustellen

ECL3 Das Lernmaterial war ungünstig gestaltet

ECL4 Die Gestaltung des Lernmaterials machte es schwierig, wichtige Informationen zügig zu finden

ECL5 Aufgrund der Gestaltung des Lernmaterials hatte ich das Gefühl, mich nicht auf die Lerninhalte konzentrieren zu können

GCL

GCL1 Ich habe aktiv über die Lerninhalte nachgedacht

GCL3 Ich habe mich bemüht, die Lerninhalte zu verstehen

GCL5 Ich habe ein umfassendes Verständnis der Lerninhalte erlangt

GCL6 Ich konnte mein bestehendes Wissen mit den Lerninhalten erweitern

GCL7 Das Wissen, das ich durch das Lernmaterial erworben habe, kann ich schnell und sicher anwenden

Appendix C
RIMMS (Loorbach et al., 2015)

Table C1

Original and Translated Items of the Reduced Instructional Materials Motivation Survey.

Original items in English	Translated and adapted items in German
<u>Attention</u>	
The quality of the text helped to hold my attention	Die Qualität der Applikation hat dazu beigetragen, meine Aufmerksamkeit zu erhalten
The way the information is arranged on the pages helped keep my attention	Die Art und Weise, wie die Informationen in der Applikation angeordnet sind, trug dazu bei, meine Aufmerksamkeit zu erhalten.
The variety of reading passages, exercises, illustrations, etc., helped keep my attention on the user instructions	Die Vielfalt der Passagen, Übungen, Illustrationen usw. trug dazu bei, meine Aufmerksamkeit auf die Benutzeranweisungen zu lenken.
<u>Relevance</u>	
It is clear to me how the content of these user instructions is related to things I already know	Es ist mir klar, wie der Inhalt mit Dingen zusammenhängt, die ich bereits kenne.
The content and style of writing in these user instructions convey the impression that being able to work with the telephone is worth it	Der Inhalt und der Stil der Applikation vermitteln den Eindruck, dass es sich lohnt, mit dieser Applikation zu arbeiten.
The content of these user instructions will be useful to me	Der Inhalt der Applikation wird für mich nützlich sein.
<u>Confidence</u>	
As I worked with these user instructions, I was confident that I could learn how to work well with the telephone	Als ich mit der Applikation arbeitete, war ich zuversichtlich, dass ich lernen würde, gut damit zu arbeiten.

After working with these user instructions for a while, I was confident that I would be able to complete exercises with the telephone

Nachdem ich eine Weile mit dem der Applikation gearbeitet hatte, war ich zuversichtlich, dass ich in der Lage sein würde, das T-Shirt mithilfe der Applikation zu falten.

The good organization of the content helped me be confident that I would learn to work with the telephone

Die gute Gliederung des Inhalts gab mir die Gewissheit, dass ich lernen würde, mit der Applikation zu arbeiten.

Satisfaction

I enjoyed working with these user instructions so much that I was stimulated to keep on working

Die Arbeit mit der Applikation hat mir so viel Spass gemacht, dass mich das zum Weitermachen animiert hat.

I really enjoyed working with these user instructions

Es hat mir wirklich Spass gemacht, mit der Applikation zu arbeiten.

It was a pleasure to work with such well-designed user instructions

Es war ein Vergnügen, mit einer so gut durchdachten Applikation zu arbeiten.

Note. Original RIMMS items were translated to German and adapted by the author to fit the context of learning with an AR application.